

Protonation Studies of some *N*-Substituted Hydroxamic Acids[#]

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The acid-catalysed hydrolysis of hydroxamic acids is a widely studied organic reaction¹. The acid-base properties of organic compounds are among the most relevant factors affecting their reactivity and therefore studies leading to the definition of such properties through equilibrium measurement yield extremely valuable data for the elucidation of reaction mechanism. In contrast to the widely studied acid-base properties of the carbonyl group², analogous hydroxamic acids have received little attention³. This prompted us to undertake the present investigation of protonation equilibrium of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) and two of its derivatives (4-Cl PBHA and 4-CH₃ PBHA) in sulphuric acid. The Hammett acidity function method (HAFM)⁴, the Bunnett-Olsen method (BOM)⁵ and Cox-Yates excess acidity method (EAM)⁶ have been compared in order to rationalise the differences observed between pK_{BH^+} values estimated by each classical method. The behaviour of hydroxamic acid and the conditions of its use in strongly acidic media will be useful for analytical reactions.

Results and Discussion

Hydroxamic acids behave as weak acids (pK_a in the range 8–9) and, like most carbonyl compounds, they are also weak bases. A well established method for the quantitative study of acid-base equilibria involves monitoring some spectral change as a function K_{BH^+} of some measure of the acid and base strength of solution.

The protonation acidity constant (pK_{BH^+}) were determined uv-spectrophotometrically by measuring the

ionisation ratio ($C_{BH^+}/C_B = I$) in concentrated sulphuric acid solution containing 10% (v/v) dioxane. The change observed with increasing acidity is from a spectrum characteristic of the unprotonated base (B) to that of the protonated base (BH⁺). Protonation data have been calculated by three different methods (Table 1) as follows.

(i) The first method is the Hammett method⁴ suitably modified by using the acidity function appropriate to the 'class' of bases under consideration. For each compound pK_{BH^+} was obtained by plotting $\log I$ against H_A according to equation (2), where C_{BH^+} and C_B are molar concentrations of conjugate acid and base respectively,

$$\log C_{BH^+}/C_B = \log I = -mH_A + pK_{BH^+} \quad (2)$$

where I is the ionisation ratio ($[BH^+]/[B] = I$) and H_A the amide acidity function. The pK_{BH^+} values are presented in Table 1. The Hammett approach was found not to be general.

(ii) A more general approach was desired and in fact proposed by Bunnett and Olsen⁵ on the basis of linear free energy relationship. Modena and Scorrano⁷ formulated equation (3),

$$\log I - \log C_{H^+} = (1-\phi)(H_0 + \log C_{H^+}) + pK_{BH^+} \quad (3)$$

In this method, for each compound pK_{BH^+} was obtained by plotting ($\log I - \log C_{H^+}$) against ($H_0 + \log C_{H^+}$). The $(1-\phi)$ and pK_{BH^+} values are presented in Table 1.

(iii) Cox and Yates developed a method for obtaining accurate pK_{BH^+} values, in spite of possible medium effects, based on the excess acidity (X), which is a measure of the deviation of the acid system from

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TABLE 1— pK_{BH^+} VALUES FOR HYDROXAMIC ACIDS CALCULATED BY DIFFERENT METHODS*

Hydroxamic acid $C_6H_5N(OH)(C=O)C_6H_4-X$	HAFM				BOM				EAM			
	pK_{BH^+}	n	m	r	pK_{BH^+}	n	$(1-\phi)$	r	pK_{BH^+}	n	m^*	r
X												
H	-1.91	7	0.48	0.963	-2.11	5	0.71	0.997	-2.24	5	0.37	0.990
4-CH ₃	-1.51	6	0.46	0.995	-1.44	6	0.74	0.995	-1.78	6	0.35	0.990
4-Cl	-2.57	10	1.46	0.987	-2.28	11	1.12	0.986	-2.37	11	1.16	0.989

* n = number of points, r = correlation coefficient.

ideality with increasing acid concentrations^{6,8}. According to this method, pK_{BH^+} values are determined as intercepts by plotting the left-hand-side of equation (4) against X values,

$$\log I - \log C_{H^+} = m^* X + pK_{BH^+} \quad (4)$$

The slope (m^*) is characteristic of the protonation behaviour of the hydroxamic acids under consideration. The m^* values (Table 1) offer no real clues to the behaviour of these compounds. By analogy with Bunnett-Olsen ϕ values, $m^* > 1$ should indicate a larger than usual change in solvation by water molecules in going from $(B + H^+)$ to BH^+ , and $m^* < 1$ should indicate the opposite. The m^* values (Table 1) for PBHA, 4-CH₃ PBHA and 4-Cl PBHA, which are quite close to that reported⁶ for nitrogen bases such as primary anilines. The agreement among pK_{BH^+} values calculated by equations (2) to (4) is good. All the linear regression plots are less satisfactory and show a scattering of points, which could only be resolved into straight lines by omitting certain points and considering limited acid concentration range.

Theoretical and practical aspects⁹ of the above methods have been treated extensively. The values of pK_{BH^+} (Table 1) show a regular variation with substituents: electron-withdrawing group (4-Cl PBHA) decreases and electron-donating group (4-CH₃ PBHA) increases the pK_{BH^+} . The data indicate that 4-CH₃ PBHA is more basic than PBHA. This means that methyl group is capable of increasing the electron density at the carbonyl oxygen.

The position of λ_{max} of hydroxamic acids remained constant in solution upto 7 M H₂SO₄, but in more concentrated acid there was a steady bathochromic shift.

At the same time, the absorbance at the position of λ_{max} decreased as the solvent was varied. For these pK_{BH^+} was calculated by considering the absorbances at λ_{max} irrespective of the wavelength at which maximum occurs.

Experimental

PBHA, 4-CH₃ PBHA and 4-Cl PBHA were prepared by a standard method¹⁰ and purified by crystallisation from ether and benzene.

Concentrated sulphuric acid was standardised against standard sodium hydroxide. Acid solutions of appropriate concentrations were made up by diluting with distilled water. The samples were prepared by dilution of equivalent small portions (1 ml) of an dioxane solution of the substrate with the appropriate acid solutions. Solutions were cooled in an ice-bath before and during the addition. The resulting cold solution was then thermostated to $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The solutions were then transferred into 10 mm glass cells and spectra recorded against acid solutions of the molarity, near λ_{max} of the base B. The molarities of the substrates were around 3.5×10^{-5} M. The absorbance (A) was recorded immediately after the addition of the substrate. The ionisation ratio (I) was calculated from equation (5) where A_B is the absorbance of the unprotonated substrate and A_{BH^+} that of its conjugate acid,

$$I = [BH^+]/[B] = (A_B - A) / (A - A_{BH^+}) \quad (5)$$

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